

The Role of Indigenous Institutions in Resolving Intergroup Conflict: A Case Study of the Inter-Ethnic Conflict Between Argobba and Afar People in Northeast Ethiopia

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Abstract: *This study delves into the pivotal role of indigenous institutions in resolving inter-ethnic conflicts, with a specific focus on the ongoing dispute between the Afar and Argobba communities in northeastern Ethiopia. It uses a mix of in-depth qualitative approaches, namely interviews, focus group discussions, non-participant observation, case stories and document analysis, to assess the effectiveness of indigenous institutions such as the Abeggar, religious leaders and clan leaders in inter-group conflict management and reconciliation. The findings of the study revealed the critical importance of indigenous institutions in inter-group conflict resolution in the study area, given their legitimacy, community trust and recognized authority. The indigenous institutions employ a mix of unique conflict resolution methods which are deeply rooted in the cultural practices and values of the communities, notably mediation and reconciliation. Nevertheless, the study emphasizes the imperative for increased state recognition of indigenous institutions and their integration into formal conflict management processes in order to enhance the capacities of these institutions for more effective conflict resolution and peace-building services within the region. This research offers valuable recommendations for policymakers and practitioners to capitalize on the strengths of indigenous institutions and integrate them into formal governance systems. It also contributes to the expanding body of literature on the role of indigenous institutions in conflict resolution, reaffirming the significance of engaging with local communities and their institutions in the pursuit of sustainable peace-building initiatives.*

Keywords: Indigenous Institutions, Inter-ethnic Conflict, Conflict Resolution, Afar and Argobba communities, Abeggar, Clan leader, Qualitative approach.

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1. Introduction

Chief Linchwe II of Botswana claimed that ‘In Botswana, the people still rally more behind the chief than behind the politicians’ (1997, quoted in Logan 2008, 1). This claim holds true for many African countries. It is no wonder that the 1990s decentralization reforms in Africa have further enhanced the influence of traditional leaders, chiefs and elders at local levels (Erk 2014). In many African countries, traditional authorities are providing essential collective goods that elected local authorities failed to deliver (Wunsch 2008). Traditional authorities play a supreme role as mediators of violent intra-ethnic and inter-ethnic conflicts at local levels (ibid.).

Obviously, conflict is inherent in every human society, with its manifestations varying across different cultures and regions. Ethnic conflicts, state fragilities and instabilities persist in various parts of the world. In the post-independence period, Africa faces numerous challenges and disagreements related to ethnic and religious tensions, resource competition, border disputes, leadership

shortcomings, and corruption, poverty, and governance issues (Bello 2016; Kariuki 2009). The Horn of Africa in particular is notorious for its complexity and conflicts, stemming from political rivalries between nations and violence rooted in inter-ethnic disputes (Tigist 2014).

Despite numerous examples of conflicts in sub-Saharan African countries, African societies have developed customary conflict resolution methods that have been practiced in Africa for generations to efficiently and sustainably manage and resolve their conflicts (Wassara 2007). As a result, traditional leadership, based on cultural values and practices, is a legally recognized form of governance in some African countries. The study by Logan clearly demonstrates that traditional authorities, chiefs, and elders continue to play a crucial role in conflict resolution, not only for Africans but also for people worldwide. They act as intermediaries in resolving both violent and nonviolent disputes in numerous African nations (Logan 2008).

Ethiopia is the home of over 80 ethno-linguistic communities, each possessing distinct cultures, languages, histories, customary law, and methods of conflict resolution. These communities share many values and cultural practices that have enabled them to live in coexistence for centuries. Each community utilizes indigenous conflict resolution mechanisms as a healing process, offering alternatives for positive decisions and structured political, judicial, and arbitration mechanisms. These systems, integral to cultural heritage, play proactive roles in promoting social cohesion and reactivation roles in dispute resolution (Ramani & Zhimin 2010). Different Ethiopian communities, such as Gamo, Oromo, Afar, Amhara and others, widely practice indigenous conflict resolution, showcasing its importance in restoring balance, settling conflicts and eliminating disputes. The Gadaa system among the Oromo people and elder councils across different ethnic communities, for example, uses distinctive methods that have been effective for centuries in rural areas, though it is facing decline with modernization (Pankhurst & Assefa 2008). These institutions emphasize consensus-based decision-making, mediation by respected figures, restorative justice, group harmony and traditional rituals to ensure peace (Ambaye, 2008; Mekonnen 2016). The customary elders identify root causes, involving all parties to address underlying issues and leading to reconciliation, compensation, or forgiveness. They continue to play a vital role in settling disputes, drawing on heritage, customs and norms to foster recovery, reconciliation, and community unity. These indigenous conflict resolution institutions coexist with the formal legal system and present an accessible alternative to the state judiciary system, especially in the rural area (Abera 2000).

However, in recent years, indigenous conflict resolution institutions in Ethiopia have been limited by complex and multifaceted conflicts, often ignited by inter-ethnic disputes, which in turn affect symbiotic relations among ethnic communities. Some observers even cast doubt on their potential to address conflicts arising in inter-group relations (Abbink 2006). The Afar and Argobba communities in northeast Ethiopia have not remained immune to such conflicts. The inter-ethnic conflict between the Argobba and Afar people has deep historical roots, stemming from issues related to land ownership, resource allocation and cultural differences (Endris Ali 2021). Both ethnic groups have competing claims to certain territories, which has led to tensions, disputes and even violent confrontations. The recurring violent incidents between the Afar and Argobba communities exemplify one of the challenges that the country is facing today.

While indigenous institutions have usually played an effective role in resolving small-scale conflicts within each community, the potential and limits of indigenous institutions in dealing with conflicts between the Afar and Argobba communities remain underexplored. Academic studies by Azmera (2013) and Muktar (2019) have highlighted the inability of past top-down mediation efforts to resolve the conflicts effectively. On the other hand, the role of indigenous institutions in resolving inter-ethnic conflicts has gained attention in recent research by scholars (like Endris Ali, (2021), Kelemework, 2011, and Missaye, 2022,) but the practice of these institutions is currently limited due to a lack of recognition and awareness (Muauz Gidey 2013).

Thus, this article aims to examine the role of indigenous institutions in resolving inter-ethnic conflicts, focusing on the Afar and Argobba communities. It specifically aims to identify the

conflict resolution employed to address their disputed issues, examine the effectiveness of their institutions of conflict resolution, and identify factors that constrain their potential to prevent and transform inter-ethnic conflicts.

The study theorizes indigenous institutions as social capital that prioritizes social networks, relationships, and trust to address conflict among groups. The indigenous institutions, acting as vital arenas for conflict resolution, function as bridges between communities during interethnic conflicts. This view helps us dissect how the social connections within the Argobba and Afar indigenous institutions contribute to conflict resolution and maintain social cohesion. Additionally, considering indigenous institutions of conflict resolution as part of shared cultural values and practices that promote peaceful coexistence, the Cultural Hegemony Theory adds depth to our understanding. It explores how dominant cultural values and norms within these institutions shape the processes of conflict resolution, emphasizing the role of cultural hegemony in maintaining social order and contributing to the solidarity within the Argobba and Afar communities. Furthermore, incorporating the Resource Dependence Theory into this analysis would provide insight into how the availability and distribution of resources within these indigenous institutions influence their effectiveness in resolving conflicts and fostering social cohesion. The theories mentioned—social capital through indigenous institutions, Cultural Hegemony Theory, and Resource Dependence Theory—are crucial for comprehending the dynamics of conflict resolution between the Argobba and Afar people in Northeast Ethiopia. They shed light on social connections, cultural values, and resource dynamics that play pivotal roles in maintaining social cohesion during interethnic conflicts.

The remainder of the article is split into three sections. The second section describes the study designs and methods used for data collection and analysis. The third section contains the findings and discussions based on evidence of conflict resolution in the study contexts. The last section provides a conclusion and recommendations.

2. Research Design and Methods

For a comprehensive exploration of indigenous conflict resolution methods among the Afar and Argoba ethnic groups, this study employed a mix of in-depth qualitative research approaches. This method, emphasizing exploration and understanding of events and human behaviors, is well-suited for social science research (Creswell 2007). The exploratory design used for the study facilitated in-depth knowledge acquisition from key individuals in a natural setting.

The data was deduced from both primary and secondary sources. Primary data, directly related to the exploration content, was obtained through in-depth interviews, focus group discussions, and non-participant observation. Secondary data included books, reports, legal documents, and online articles, contributing fresh perspectives.

In total, twenty individuals, comprising clan leaders, farmers, government employees, religious leaders, and district police, were interviewed. Semi-structured interviews were preferred for their flexibility while maintaining guidance. Face-to-face interviews enhanced the credibility and importance of the research.

In addition, two focus group discussions, each consisting of seven participants, were conducted. The focus group discussants included clan leaders, abeggars, religious leaders, and local members. The focus group discussions specifically complemented and validated information gathered from individual interviews.

Furthermore, direct observation in Medina and Telalak districts provided insights into conflict resolution processes. This method addressed potential contradictions between the verbal and behavioral expressions of the informants. Secondary sources proved to be useful in filling gaps in the data acquired from interviews and observations.

Finally, we transcribed and translated the interviews and field notes in order to identify key themes. Data were organized according to research objectives, with thematic classification covering conflict sources, resolution techniques, stakeholder participation, and indigenous-institution-state-law linkages. The data collection, analysis, and writing of the findings of the study were guided by indigenous research principles such as reciprocity, respect, accountability, and ethical awareness of contexts and informants.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1 Overview of Inter-Ethnic Conflicts in Ethiopia

Inter-ethnic conflicts in Ethiopia have been a significant issue for many years. Ethiopia is a diverse country with over 80 different ethnic groups, each with their own language, culture, and traditions. Ethnic diversity in the country, as it has been seen as a blessing and source of strength, has also been a trigger for conflicts throughout the nation's history. These conflicts arise due to a variety of factors, including competition for resources, historical grievances, political power struggles, and territorial disputes. One of the most notable interethnic conflicts is the Oromo-Amhara conflict, between the two largest ethnic groups in Ethiopia. Their conflict has its origins in political, economic, and historical grievances, including issues of land ownership, representation, and power sharing. Likewise, there has been conflict between the Somali and Oromo communities. Their conflict is often related to territorial or border disputes, competition over resources, and political representation in local government structures.

Furthermore, the Afar and Issa communities have experienced conflicts, especially in the Afar and Somali regional states. Their conflicts are primarily driven by competition for grazing land and water resources, along with historical grievances and political rivalries. In recent years, the Tigray and Amhara ethnic groups have experienced conflict that has escalated into widespread armed struggle in the country. The key source of their conflict revolves around a wide variety of grievances related to territorial claims, border disputes, power struggles, and historical grievances. There has also been recurring conflict in the multiethnic Benishangul-Gumuz region, especially between the Gumuz and Amhara communities, over issues related to historical land rights, indigenous people rights, and political representation.

Likewise, the Gambela region has experienced recurring conflicts among indigenous communities such as Anuak and Neur as well as between the indigenous communities and 'settlers' from other regions of the country. These conflicts have been rooted in disputes over land and other natural resources, socio-economic marginalization, and political representation of the highlanders in the region. The former Southern Nations, Nationalities, and

Peoples' Region (SNNPR) witnessed interethnic conflicts between various ethnic communities such as the Konso versus Derashe, the Gedeo versus Guji, and Sidama versus Wolaita, mainly due to land disputes, resource competition, and political representation struggles.

What is common in the above-mentioned conflicts is that they are influenced by political factors such as unequal representation, competition for resources, injustices dating back to different regimes, and rivalries among political parties and are routinely led by local political elites. In addition, these conflicts have resulted in widespread internal displacement, loss of life, and social unrest, which are difficult to manage with the conflict resolution strategies used in the grassroots communities. As a result, the Ethiopian government has been trying to address these conflicts through a variety of strategies, such as inter-communal dialogue and mediation, implementing policies like referendums for equitable resource distribution and border demarcation, and encouraging inter-ethnic cooperation and mutual development projects, though such measures frequently fail or trigger the reoccurrence of the conflict as they do not genuinely utilize the customary institutions that complement top-down measures.

3.2 Overview of the Afar-Argobba Inter-Ethnic Conflict

The Afar and Argoba are two ethnic groups found in northeast Ethiopia. The Afars mainly inhabit the Afar Regional State, while the Argoba people are concentrated in the Argoba Special Woreda of the Amhara Regional State. The conflict between the Afar and Argobba is complex and rooted in historical, socio-economic, and political factors. The recurring conflicts between them have resulted in violent clashes, including armed confrontations, destruction of property, displacement, and loss of lives. Retaliatory attacks from both sides have perpetuated a cycle of violence. The humanitarian impact of the conflict has been severe, with displacement, damage to infrastructure, disruptions to livelihoods, and deprivation of basic services such as healthcare and education.

The conflict between the Afar and Argoba had its roots in a land dispute. The dispute over land was and is still a key driver of their conflict. Over the years, the Afar pastoralists and the Argoba farmers have clashed over competing land uses, ownership, and access to natural resources, such as water and grazing land. But their disputes have been exacerbated by changes in regional administrative boundaries. Regarding this and related issues, the following statement by the respondent from Medina Special District in an interview summarizes:

Personally, I don't have that much information about the root causes of the recent conflict between the two cultural groups. However, historically, there have been conflicts between these two groups over access to resources such as water, grazing land, fertile soil, and revenge. Additionally, there have been boundary disputes between the two groups, leading to tensions and violence at times. Ethnic and political differences have also played a role in fueling the conflict.

In addition, the differences in the livelihoods of the Afar and Argoba communities play a significant role in the conflict. The Afar people are primarily pastoralists, relying on animal husbandry and known for their nomadic lifestyle. On the other hand, the Argoba are predominantly farmers, cultivating crops like corn, sorghum, and cotton. The competition for scarce resources, coupled with environmental degradation and climate change, has

intensified competition and conflicts as both communities struggled to sustain their livelihoods. Key informants and focus group participants identified territorial expansion, competition for resources such as water and land, ethnic rivalries, and revenge as the primary causes of conflict in the area. They relate the conflict in the area to the scarcity of resources in the area, which is related to environmental degradation, population growth, natural resource depletion and climate change.

The elders stated that recent clashes between the two cultural groups were primarily over access and use of resources, such as farmland, grazing areas, and water. Sometimes, the conflicts arose due to damage caused by Afar cattle entering Argobba farmland. Based on discussions with local individuals, it appeared that competition over grazing land and water resources was prevalent among the communities. Resource scarcity led to increased levels of violent conflict and tension between the two ethnic groups. During the discussion, a perspective was presented by a farmer from the Argobba ethnic group who is involved in the conflict with Afar pastoralists. This perspective was shared by an elderly key informant, as follows:

As a farmer, I understand the traditional way of life of pastoralists and their need for grazing lands for their livestock. However, the increasing frequency and intensity of conflicts with them over land use and resources have become a significant concern for my community. The encroachment of their animals onto our farms has resulted in crop damage, loss of income, and even violence. We have tried to find solutions through dialogue and negotiation, but the situation remains challenging. We hope that a sustainable resolution can be reached that respects the rights and livelihoods of both farming and pastoralist communities.

Another respondent who is working in Medina, Argobba Special woreda suggests that the livelihood of those who lead a pastoral lifestyle is heavily influenced by the amount and quality of their livestock, as well as the availability of water and grazing lands. These factors are all interconnected and are particularly concerning in the months of April through June, when both sources become scarce. This often results in clashes between neighboring pastoralists who are searching for these limited resources. This informant believes that prolonged periods of drought can trigger conflicts among pastoral communities that share limited resources. The Afar and Argobba societies have traditionally negotiated access to and use of natural resources such as pastures, water sources, and forests. However, the shortage of these resources due to overgrazing and drought has led to their degradation. The reduced availability of resources has impeded the free movement of pastoralists across boundaries, resulting in increased conflict and instability between these two ethnic groups.

The presence of bad traditional practices like blood revenge killings between the groups has had an influence on escalating their conflict. Interviews highlighted the cultural importance of avenging a family member's death, contributing to an ongoing cycle of violence between the two ethnic groups. The results from the focus group discussions with the Argobba informants show that the two factions sought retribution for the deaths of their members. The information received from the Afar and Argoba communities showed that the Argoba were the first to take action by killing a member of the Afar group, and the cycle of retaliation between the two groups has persisted till present times. During the fieldwork,

we had the opportunity to interview multiple locals from both sides on our Focus Group Discussions about their views regarding blood revenge in the study area. The general consensus amongst those we spoke to was that blood revenge is a serious act and an important aspect of their culture. Many believe that it is necessary to protect the honor of their family and community. In fact, it was stated that failure to avenge a family member's death can result in shame and dishonor. Nevertheless, there were some people who had apprehensions regarding the adverse effects of blood revenge on the families of the victim and the perpetrator, which can result in an unending cycle of violence spanning across multiple generations.

One of the respondents we interviewed says that the act of blood revenge is a grave matter where the family of the victim seeks to kill the murderer and their kin. This tradition is deeply rooted in Ethiopian culture, and not retaliating is seen as a sign of moral deficiency, even for the entire family. If the victim's family seeks monetary compensation instead of revenge, it could be viewed as weakness and dishonor. Despite efforts by the government's justice system, the risk of retaliation remains, as the victim's family is expected to take revenge even after the murderer has served their time. Only through intervention by abegars or clan leaders can the conflict be resolved and both parties live in peace.

There is also an issue of representation and marginalization fueling their conflict. The Afar people have at times claimed marginalization and unequal representation in governance structures, feeling that their needs and interests are not adequately addressed by the central authorities. Additionally, some argue that political figures, driven by interparty rivalries, have manipulated the conflicts for their own political gains, exacerbating interethnic tensions between the groups.

3.3 The Practice of Indigenous Institutions in Resolving Conflicts in the Study Area

The integral function of indigenous institutions in conflict resolution within the Afar and Argoba communities is deeply rooted in the cultural traditions and norms of these societies. Centuries-old practices have been employed by these institutions to address disputes and foster social harmony, drawing upon the wisdom of respected elders, religious leaders, community figures and influencers. Each ethnic group has time-tested conflict resolution institutions that they use to address disputes and conflicts that arise within the community and in their everyday relations.

The Argobba employ a unique conflict resolution system known as "Abeggar," which has deep cultural roots and operates outside of the western-oriented court system in the country. Since the Argobbas have been exposed to the influence of Christianity and Islam, their traditional dispute resolution mechanisms visibly integrate principles of peaceful conflict resolution from these religions.

Specifically, the Abeggar system among the Argobba serves as an indigenous justice method. It regulates various aspects of life, including social, political, economic, and religious matters. The Abaggar, a knowledgeable individual respected within the community, leads this system. Using a process called guma, the Abaggar reconciles conflicts by compensating victims during or after disputes, aiming for both short-term resolution and long-term peace.

The Abeggar conflict resolution process involves conflicting parties agreeing to participate, presenting their cases to a group of elders acting as mediators, and the Abeggar making a decision based on evidence and cultural norms. The implementation of solutions requires mutual agreement and collaboration. Disobeying the abeggar's decisions may lead to societal sanctions, reflecting the reverence and authority they hold in regions like Southern and Northern Wollo.

Abeggars not only resolve disputes within Argobba communities but also play a crucial role in mediating conflicts between neighboring ethnic groups. They prioritize society's safety, teach peace and the common good, and are respected as peacemakers. Success stories highlight their ability to prevent conflicts' escalation through trust-building and open communication.

During interviews, an Abeggar emphasized their deep knowledge of community customs and traditions, positioning them uniquely to promote dialogue and reconciliation between different groups. The Abeggar system remains a vital part of Argobba culture, fostering harmony, reconciliation, and the restoration of relationships within and beyond their communities.

Likewise, the Afar people utilize the traditional institution of "maro" to resolve conflicts, holding sessions under a tree. The maro involves a makaban (clan leader), elders, disputants, witnesses, and observers in a circle. Makabans, knowledgeable about customs, may vary from one to ten, with selected elders assisting. Excluding women, these individuals serve without formal training, receiving only food and drink for their efforts.

Maro has jurisdiction over disputes, excluding marriage, divorce, and inheritance, which are handled by Shari'a courts in urban areas. It resolves criminal cases from insults to homicide and civil cases, irrespective of monetary involvement. The process is accessible, cost-effective, and relatively swift, with minor cases resolved in a day and major clan disputes resolved within six months. The makaban serves indefinitely, ensuring impartiality and a deep understanding of customary law.

Intra-clan disputes involve kedo abba, with makaban as the final authority. Inter-clan conflicts seek resolution from neutral clan makabans, with appeals to the Sultan for boundary disputes. The Sultan's decision is ultimate, and inter-ethnic conflicts involve committees of elders and government officials from both sides.

The Afar pastoral community also employs the Mada'a system for conflict resolution, involving elders and clan leaders who adhere to traditional laws. Similar to other pastoralist groups, such as the Somali and Borana, Afar's conflict resolution focuses on intra- and inter-ethnic disputes. Clan leaders, chosen impartially, manage conflicts within Afar clans based on customary laws. Notably, the Mada'a has historically prevented conflicts from escalating to external mediation, fostering resolution through a tradition of forgiveness, elder respect, and resource compensation (Getachew 2001; Kinfu 2014). While shared institutions once facilitated conflict resolution between the Afar and Karrayyu communities, their influence has diminished over time due to complex factors.

The Afar people employ a unique conflict resolution system deeply rooted in their culture, primarily relying on clan leaders and religious figures within the framework of Afar traditional law (Mada'a). Clan leaders, essential for maintaining peace and settling disputes, uphold justice, equality, and impartiality. The Afar

community's cohesion centers on clans, each with legislative, executive, and judicial roles. Clan leaders mediate conflicts, with their decisions guided by cultural norms and traditions (Voelkner 1974; Getachew 2001). In interviews, community members express trust in clan leaders, emphasizing their impartiality and role in fostering stability, peace, and protection.

Clan leaders serve as moral guides, judges, and diplomats, playing a pivotal role in reconciling conflicts within and between communities. Their influence extends beyond disputes, contributing to justice, security, and the preservation of cultural heritage. Despite challenges and evolving circumstances, clan leaders remain instrumental in conflict resolution, ensuring sustainable and peaceful outcomes. The Afar's reliance on restorative justice, community engagement, and adherence to cultural norms sets their conflict resolution practices apart, promoting peaceful coexistence with neighboring tribes and effective resolution of internal conflicts.

The above-mentioned indigenous institutions of both groups excel not only in facilitating participatory and inclusive dialogue within a group but also in emphasizing restorative justice and reconciliation between groups. The emphasis on repairing relationships and addressing underlying causes distinguishes these methods from punitive measures. Insights from the study reveal that local elders, in particular, have been pivotal in advising communities to minimize conflicts. As articulated by an interviewee, "we always advise the conflicting parties to solve their conflict through local elders. Because the decision passed by the court or formal conflict resolution systems is not good for social relationships, it leads to revenge in the community" (interviewed with The Abeggar in his home in Medina District, March 2023).

The conflict resolution systems of the communities extend beyond resolving immediate disputes; they play a crucial role in developing future relationships among conflicting parties. Participants in the study underscored the simplicity, time efficiency, and cost-effectiveness of these indigenous mechanisms compared to modern approaches. A testimonial from a resident of Afar further exemplifies how indigenous institutions provided a constructive resolution to a conflict over shared resources. The respondent, who is living in Telalak, Afar district and whom we interviewed, provided his testimony about the service he got from the indigenous institutions as follows:

I had a conflict with my neighbor over the use of a shared water source on our land. We tried to solve the issue between ourselves, but it became heated and contentious, reaching a point where we couldn't find a middle ground. I was desperate for a solution, so I decided to reach out to the Makaban of the neutral clan leader for help. The staffs were very professional and welcoming. They took the time to understand the nature of our conflict and our concerns. They recognized the need to integrate traditional indigenous values and practices into the process. They facilitated a community justice circle and invited respected elders, as well as members of our respective clan leaders and families, to participate. Together, they provided guidance and support in reaching a resolution that was equitable and satisfactory for all parties. I totally appreciate the support I received from the institution, which not only helped resolve the conflict but also deepened my understanding and appreciation of indigenous values and practices. I am grateful for their role in bringing harmony to our community.

Drawing a sharp contrast, community members expressed dissatisfaction with modern legal systems, citing inefficiencies, delays, and inappropriate decisions that often lead to further conflicts. Indigenous institutions, according to the respondent from Argobba, prioritize community over justice, promoting consensus-based decision-making that restores balance between individuals, communities, and nature. Following this, he praised the role of clan leaders and religious leaders in the community and explained the weakness of the modern legal systems and the abuse they inflict on people with the following idea:

If I go to a modern court, there will be many ups and downs. They waste my time by making me go through many court doors by making appointments, but they don't give quick responses or decisions on our issues. They are not only time consumers, but I will also spend a lot of money on that matter during the court process. And when the final decision is passed, they will pass inappropriate decisions, thus bringing us back into conflict.

Furthermore, these institutions are characterized by their focus on community-based solutions, utilizing local knowledge and practices for context-specific resolutions that are readily accepted by community members. Testimonies from the Argobba ethnic community highlight the Abeggar's pivotal role in settling disputes, fostering peace, and enabling the return of displaced individuals after ethnic-based conflicts. One informant from Argobba special district also adds his testimony about the indigenous institutions by comparing them with the modern legal system. As he said, Indigenous institutions often prioritize community over justice, and the decision-making process is based on consensus and consultation. On the other hand, the modern legal system emphasizes individual rights, and decisions are made by a single authority, whether a judge or a jury. The other thing that makes them different is that indigenous institutions aim to restore the balance between the individual, the community, and nature, while the modern ones focus on punishment and rehabilitation.

Furthermore, individuals belonging to the Argobba ethnic community emphasized the significance and reliability of the abeggar in settling disputes. During an interview with a representative of the Argobba ethnic group, a key informant elaborated on the function of the abeggar in the following manner:

The Abeggar is a very successful dispute resolution system to settle peace and tolerance between our ethnic group and other neighboring ethnic groups, like the Afar and Oromo ethnic groups. To mention an example, there was an ethnic-based conflict that occurred between us (the Argobba) and Afar. The conflict caused many displacements and migrations, resulting in the loss of human life and property for both ethnic groups. Following this, the abeggar plays a critical role in the resolution process. And finally, the conflict was solved through indigenous mediation, and the displaced peoples have returned to their districts.

The efficacy of indigenous institutions extends beyond conflict resolution; they excel in promoting healing and reconciliation. Their approaches prioritize empathy, forgiveness, and understanding, fostering a sense of community ownership over conflicts. Recognizing the Abeggar and other elders' time-tested experiences, individuals emphasize their invaluable roles in any efforts to promote peace and reconciliation. Notably, indigenous institutions are not confined to resolving local disputes; they contribute significantly to stabilizing communities during

challenging times. A representative from the Afar community affirms the substantial role played by these institutions in ensuring sustainable peace for local communities. He testifies about the significant contribution played by indigenous institutions in maintaining long-lasting peace within the local communities, as follows:

As an observer of traditional societies and cultures, I have witnessed the powerful and significant role that traditional elders play in building peace. Referred to as guardians of community values, traditional elders are called upon to provide guidance and mediation during conflicts, showcasing their unwavering commitment to the welfare of their communities. Beyond conflict resolution, traditional elders play a vital role in establishing community norms, promoting social cohesion, and passing down knowledge and skills to younger generations. In a world often beleaguered by conflict and divisiveness, the role of traditional elders becomes increasingly important, inspiring a commitment to the greater good in our lives and communities.

In conclusion, the significance of indigenous institutions in settling disputes among the Afar and Argobba societies cannot be overstated. These institutions provide a culturally sensitive and community-driven approach to conflict resolution, promoting social cohesion, and maintaining peace. Their time-tested practices offer valuable lessons for fostering harmony in diverse communities.

3.4 Effectiveness of Indigenous Institutions in Resolving the Argobba-Afar Conflict

The effectiveness of indigenous institutions in resolving the Argobba-Afar conflict is noteworthy, as these traditional mechanisms play a crucial part in addressing controversies between the two communities. Indigenous conflict resolution practices, involving elders and religious leaders, have historically contributed to maintaining peace and fostering understanding between the Argobba and Afar people. The Mada'a of Afar, with its customary laws and clan leaders, has been instrumental in managing conflicts, demonstrating a commitment to peaceful resolution.

Despite challenges such as financial constraints and the need for government support, the indigenous conflict resolution system has proven effective in precluding escalation and easing conciliation. Local leaders, including clan leaders and religious figures, have actively engaged in resolving conflicts, emphasizing their role as intercessors and judges. The integration of indigenous institutions into the community fabric has allowed for the swift resolution of disputes, with decisions often based on cultural norms, traditions, and a commitment to justice.

The community's reliance on these traditional conflict resolution practices has contributed to a history of successful dispute resolution between the Argobba and Afar communities. By leveraging their knowledge of local dynamics and employing restorative justice principles, these institutions have fostered stability, peace, and coexistence. Let us briefly present two case stories that reveal the effectiveness of the indigenous institutions in resolving conflict between the Afar and Argobba.

Case 1: Resolving Land and Water Disputes

As already noted above, the Afar and Argobba ethnic groups have grappled with a prolonged conflict rooted in historical land

disputes and political representation. The focal point of contention revolves around access to vital resources—pasture and grazing lands crucial for the survival of both communities. The Afar pastoralists depend on regional water points for their livestock, while the Argobba farmers require water for irrigating crops.

Complicating matters, the Afar traditionally graze their livestock on communal land, while the Argobba cultivate crops on individual plots. Tensions peaked in June 2015 when the Afar grazed their livestock on land claimed by the Argobba, resulting in crop damage and heightened conflict. This clash, marked by accusations of resource theft and destruction, led to violence and bloodshed.

To address this ongoing strife, traditional elders from both communities convened in a series of town hall meetings and negotiations. Employing customary laws and traditional dispute resolution mechanisms, these elders worked towards fostering a more peaceful coexistence. A joint committee of elders was established to manage water points, ensuring equitable access for both farmers and pastoralists. This committee also played a crucial role in arbitrating disputes to prevent further violence.

The traditional leaders promoted mutual respect and trust between the Afar and Argobba communities by encouraging participation in social events and cultural festivals. This initiative proved instrumental in improving relations, contributing to a reduction in the conflict in the area.

Case 2: Ceasing Retaliatory Violence

According to our informants, disputes over grazing areas and water sources in the remote village of Medina escalated into violent clashes, causing numerous casualties, property destruction, and widespread displacement in November 2022. The incident unfolded in the village when an anonymous attack claimed the life of an Afar man. This act triggered immediate retaliation from the Afar community, leading to an attack on a nearby Argobba village. The retaliatory violence, marked by burning houses and the loss of lives, prompted further reprisals from the Argobba community, resulting in a protracted cycle of violence.

As the conflict intensified, the Ethiopian government intervened, deploying security forces and initiating a top-down peace dialogue between the two communities. However, these efforts faced substantial challenges due to deep-seated distrust and animosity between the conflicting communities and the influence of political elites. The conflict's toll extended to the displacement of thousands, causing severe economic and social disruptions.

To break the cycle of violence, traditional elders from both sides intervened to broker a ceasefire and establish a peace process. They formed a joint peace committee comprising impartial individuals from each community and invited government officials to observe and support the negotiations. Through dialogues and negotiations facilitated by the peace committee, a truce was slowly achieved, leading to a gradual cessation of hostilities.

The peace committee of customary elders not only facilitated the return of displaced families but also initiated community-based development projects to foster inter-ethnic cooperation. According to our informants, this agreement not only resolved immediate conflicts but also laid the groundwork for cooperation, promoting long-term stability and mutual benefits for both communities.

3.5 Challenges and Opportunities for the Effectiveness of the Indigenous Institutions

Indigenous conflict resolution institutions possess notable strengths, including cost-effectiveness and accessibility, making them more available to a broader population than formal legal systems. The process emphasizes community involvement, engaging various stakeholders to foster a sense of collective responsibility. Indigenous conflict resolution demonstrates a swifter resolution compared to formal legal proceedings, ensuring timely outcomes. Public enforcement, facilitated through community sanctions, contributes to compliance and accountability. Moreover, these institutions contribute to social harmony by honoring elders, practicing forgiveness, and facilitating compensation transfers. However, they face limitations such as reliance on oral tradition, potential male dominance, a lack of early warning mechanisms, logistical challenges, and limited interest from younger generations.

Challenges further arise, including financial constraints that necessitate elders seeking funds from the community, marginalization by external actors, especially governments and international organizations, and a risk of losing traditional practices due to a lack of knowledge transfer and limited support from governments. The generational gap, fueled by the younger generation's preference for modern institutions, poses a threat to the sustainability of indigenous practices.

Despite those challenges, recognizing and supporting the role of indigenous conflict resolution institutions remains crucial for maintaining collective security, peace, and justice in communities where formal law enforcement is weak. Collaborative efforts between governmental and non-governmental organizations are essential to provide resources and training, promote inclusivity, and ensure the continued effectiveness and sustainability of these traditional practices.

In the study area, the local government is acknowledged for its involvement in supporting indigenous conflict resolution institutions, primarily through training initiatives. However, respondents highlight a significant gap, emphasizing the government's failure to provide essential financial and material support to strengthen these institutions. The criticism centers on the government's prioritization of capacity-building activities, particularly training, for traditional elders who serve as peace builders in the community. It is argued that without adequate support, these elders may struggle to effectively fulfill their crucial roles in maintaining peace and resolving conflicts at the grassroots level.

Respondents express disappointment in the government's neglect to invest in capacity building for traditional elders, considering it a failure to fulfill its duty to promote peace and stability in the region. Critiques extend to the government's preference for top-down approaches to conflict resolution, such as military intervention or political negotiations, rather than endorsing community-led initiatives led by traditional and religious elders. Advocates for these community leaders argue that they possess a nuanced understanding of local dynamics, making them better equipped to address the root causes of conflicts and promote sustainable peace.

The challenges faced by indigenous conflict resolution institutions, including a lack of legal directives, insufficient funding, and

limited oversight capacity, are acknowledged. Informants stress that traditional elders, with governmental assistance, could efficiently resolve disputes and foster harmony in their communities. As an Ethiopian citizen, the narrator attests to the pivotal role played by traditional elders in preserving cultural heritage and social cohesion. While recognizing the invaluable contribution of elders, the narrator contends that support from the government, encompassing funding, training, and recognition, enhances their effectiveness in coordinating community initiatives such as peace building. Moreover, the elders can act as a crucial link between the community and the government, effectively communicating concerns and needs.

The overall criticism of the government's approach to capacity-building activities for indigenous elders suggests a perception that the government might not be adequately supporting community-driven solutions to conflicts, relying instead on external interventions. The call is for the government to acknowledge, allocate resources, and actively support elders and spiritual leaders who play significant roles in preserving heritage and promoting social progress within communities.

4. Conclusion and Recommendations

4.1 Conclusion

As demonstrated in this article, Afar and Argobba have experienced complex conflicts in their relationships that require multifaceted approaches to resolve or transform. The Ethiopian government and regional authorities have made efforts to address the conflict by focusing on paternalistic top-down mediation, dialogues and the deployment of security forces. However, such top-down measures were unable to address the underlying causes of the conflict and ensure durable peace in the area. The study underscores the vital role of indigenous institutions, particularly in the context of resolving conflicts between the Argobba and Afar communities. Despite facing challenges such as financial constraints and limited government support, their traditional institutions and their specific mechanisms, including the Mada'a of Afar and local leaders, the Abegars, religious leaders, and clan leaders of Afar, have demonstrated effectiveness in preventing conflicts from escalating and promoting reconciliation between the groups. This success is due to their reliance on cultural norms and restorative justice principles in their conflict resolution.

4.2 Recommendations

Based on the findings from our case studies, it is crucial for the federal and regional governments to ensure community-owned dialogue and reconciliation as a guarantee for durable peace.

In times of conflict, it is crucial for governmental bodies from each group to encourage and facilitate open conversations between the two ethnic groups to promote mutual understanding and resolve tensions between them.

In addition, education and awareness should highlight the benefits of diversity, trust, tolerance, and mutual respect in the context of ethnic diversity and the role of shared values in preventing conflicts. In this regard, the indigenous institutions need to be supported, as they are accessible, fair and impartial and can prevent conflicts before they escalate.

It is also critical that the government provide adequate financial and material support to indigenous institutions, ensuring they have

the resources necessary to function effectively. This includes funding for training programs, logistical needs, and the establishment of permanent venues for conflict resolution.

The elders also need to have appreciative training programs over issues such as conflict prevention, mediation techniques, and the nuances of handling inter-ethnic disputes, empowering them to fulfill their roles more effectively.

It is always relevant to ensure the active participation of community members in conflict resolution processes led by indigenous institutions, as this ensures that the decisions of elders are widely accepted and enforced within the community.

We also recommend fostering collaboration between the government and indigenous institutions without undermining the ownership of the indigenous by the community elders. This would ensure the promotion of complementary relationships between customary and formal systems, leveraging their community-level knowledge and understanding to enhance overall conflict resolution efforts.

It is also relevant to support an initiative to document indigenous conflict resolution practices. This would help in standardizing decision-making, preserving cultural heritage, and facilitating knowledge transfer between generations.

Finally, it is crucial to engage and educate the younger generation on the significance of traditional practices, as it opens space for them to appreciate and actively participate in indigenous conflict resolution processes.

References

1. Abbink, J. (2006). Ethnicity and conflict generation in Ethiopia: Some problems and prospects of ethno-regional federalism. *Journal of contemporary African studies*, 24(3), 389-413.
2. Jembere, A., & African studies centre. (2000). *An introduction to the legal history of Ethiopia, 1434-1974* (p. 194). Lit.
3. Ambaye, O. (2008). Traditional Conflict Resolution Mechanism (TCRM): the Case of Sidama. *Making peace in Ethiopia: Five cases of Traditional mechanisms for conflict Resolution. Peace and Development committee: Addis Ababa, Ethiopia*, 101-120.
4. Azmera Wolde Hana, 2013. Ethnic Relationships in Ethiopia: The Case of Argobba and their Neighbours
5. Creswell, J. W., & Poth, C. N. (2016). *Qualitative inquiry and research design: Choosing among five approaches*. Sage publications.
6. Haider, E. A. Post-1991 inter-ethnic relations in southeastern wollo: the oromo and the afar. *Editor's Note*, 257.
7. Erk, J. (2018). Federalism and decentralization in Sub-Saharan Africa: Five patterns of evolution. In *Federalism and Decentralization in Sub-Saharan Africa* (pp. 1-18). Routledge.

8. Getachew, K. N. (2001). Among the pastoral Afar in Ethiopia: Tradition, continuity and socio-economic change. (No Title).
9. Kariuki, D. F. (2015). Conflict resolution by elders in Africa: Successes, challenges and opportunities. *Challenges and Opportunities (July 9, 2015)*.
10. Reda, K. T. (2011). Conflict and alternative dispute resolution among the Afar pastoralists of Ethiopia. *African Journal of History and Culture*, 3(3), 38.
11. Gebre-Egziabher, K. A. (2014). Dispute resolution mechanisms among the Afar People of Ethiopia and their contribution to the Development Process. *TD: The Journal for Transdisciplinary Research in Southern Africa*, 10(4), 152-164.
12. Logan, C. (2008). *Traditional leaders in modern Africa: can democracy and the chief co-exist?*. Institute for Democracy in South Africa (IDASA).
13. Mengstie, M. M. (2022). Exploring indigenous conflict resolution mechanisms between the Awi and Gumuz ethnic communities in Zigem Woreda, Ethiopia. *Journal of aggression, conflict and peace research*, 14(3), 244-258.
14. Mekonnen, D. (2016). Major features of indigenous conflict resolution mechanisms in Ethiopia. *International Journal of Arts Humanities and Social Sciences (IJAHSS)*, 1(1), 1-6.
15. Toyib, M., Balew, E., & Samara, E. (2019). Inter-ethnic conflict between afar and amhara border area around chifra woreda, since 2017 and assessing indiginious conflict resolution mechanism.
16. Alemu, M. G., (2013). The Mada'a and Mablo of the Afar: Customary system of Conflict Transformation.
17. Pankhurst, A., & Assefa, G. (Eds.). (2016). *Grass-roots justice in Ethiopia: The contribution of customary dispute resolution*. Centre français des études éthiopiennes.
18. Bello, P. O., & Olutola, A. (2016). Indigenous Conflict Resolution Mechanisms in Africa: Lessons Drawn for Nigeria. *Bangladesh e-Journal of Sociology*, 13(2).
19. Ramani, K., & Zhimin, L. (2010). A survey on conflict resolution mechanisms in public secondary schools: A case of Nairobi province, Kenya. *Educational research and reviews*, 5(5), 242.
20. Wassara, S. S. (2007). Traditional mechanisms of conflict resolution in Southern Sudan. *Berghof Foundation for Peace Support*, 1-13.
21. Feyissa, T. K. (2015). *Conflicts among Pastoralists in the Borana Area of Southern Ethiopia: The case of Borana and Garri* (Master's thesis, UiT Norges arktiske universitet).
22. Voelkner, H. E. (1974). *The Social Feasibility of Settling Semi-nomadic Afar on Irrigation Agriculture in the Awash Valley Ethiopia*.
23. Wallenstein, P. (2023). Understanding conflict resolution.
24. Wunsch, J. S. (2008, April). Why has decentralization failed in Africa? Assessing the lessons of self-organized, local governance initiatives. In *Workshop on Political Theory and Policy Analysis*. Bloomington IN: Indiana University. retrieved from http://www.indiana.edu/~workshop/seminars/papers/wunsch_mcpaper08.pdf.